

Reason, Revelation, and Sceptical Argumentation in 12th- to 14th- Century Byzantium

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Abstract:

In middle to late Byzantium, one finds dogmatic-style sceptical arguments employed against human reason in relation to divine revelation, where revelation becomes the sole criterion of certain truth in contrast to reason. This argumentative strategy originates in early Christian authors, especially Clement of Alexandria (c. 150–215 CE) and Gregory Nazianzen (c. 329–390 CE), who maintain that revelation is the only domain of knowledge where certainty is possible. Given this, one finds two striking variations of this sceptical approach: a “mild” variant (represented by Clement), where knowledge derived from human reason admits partial access to truths manifested in revelation, if imperfect; and a “strict” variant (represented by Gregory), where knowledge derived from human reason does not admit any access to truths in revelation. This paper analyzes the three Byzantines, Nicholas of Methone (d. 1160/66 CE), Theodore Metochites (1270–1320 CE), and Gregory Palamas (1296–1357/59 CE), who each display certain tendencies toward these two “poles” in their respective epistemological positions on knowledge through reason and faith.

Introduction

While the attitude concerning philosophy varied among early Christians, a common theme among many was to cast doubt on certainty attained in philosophy outside the domain of divine enlightenment: without the revelation of the one true God, the philosophers contradict themselves, and any attempt to ascertain truth purely by reason is prone to contradiction and overturning.¹ This should motivate one to strive toward the safe certainty of the true light itself: the direct manifestation of God through the divine person of Christ (i.e. the *Logos*). One can detect a parallel here to Pyrrhonian Sceptics who hold that philosophical argumentation only results in constant contradictory arguments that cannot be settled: the goal for the Sceptic, then, is to suspend judgment, and in so doing attain the state of true *ataraxia*, or serene tranquility.²

Early Christians—and, as will be this paper’s focus, later Byzantine Christians—disagree with the idea that *all* claims of truth result in contradiction and the impossibility of judgment. Yet they would concur that the end of one’s sceptical response to dubious claims concerning reality should lead to a higher state: for Christians this would be reliance on divine revelation, rather than the Sceptic’s mere “living with the appearances,” as leading to this state. Hence, the early and later Byzantine Christian version of scepticism involves a unique combination of factors: generally (a) a

¹ A classic example of this can be seen in the early Latin Christian, Tertullian: see below, p. 3 and n. 11.

² On tranquility (*ataraxia*) as the end of the Pyrrhonian Sceptic, see e.g. Sextus Empiricus, *Pyrrhoniae hypotyposes* I.25–30, I.12. The tenability of tranquility as a goal is connected with the issue of beliefs for Pyrrhonian Sceptics, a wide-ranging controversy in the literature: see e.g. Burnyeat (1980) and Frede (1987); on *ataraxia* in Sextus, see Striker (1990).

form of negative dogmatism about knowledge through human reason and philosophy; yet **(b)** the maintenance that certainty of knowledge is still possible when obtained through divine revelation. Given these two factors, two questions face us, especially when we consider later Byzantines: for **(a)**, just what is the exact feature of human reason and philosophy that makes it fail to attain its object of knowledge? And for **(b)**, what is it about revelation that merits its certainty in a way not possessed by reason **(a)**?

This paper will address these two questions by focusing on three late Byzantines—Nicholas of Methone (d. 1160/66 CE), Theodore Metochites (1270–1320 CE), and Gregory Palamas (1296–1357/59 CE)—who come at a time of revived interest in the pagan philosophical traditions, especially that of the late Neoplatonist, Proclus (c. 412–485 CE), and Neoplatonism generally, in Byzantium. Their respective discussions on human reason and what it can know outside the domain of revelation—hence in pagan philosophy—revives an old, perennial debate on reason and philosophy, and their relation to divine revelation, in 2nd- to 4th-century Christians. This paper will begin by focusing on Clement of Alexandria (140/50–220 CE) and Gregory Nazianzen (329–390 CE), representing two poles of scepticism for the later tradition: the former representing a “mild” form, wherein reason has *partial* access to the full truth, revealed in revelation, though remaining incomplete; and the latter representing a “stricter” form, wherein reason has *no* access to the full truth revealed in revelation, thus implying the futility of reason to acquire truths by its own means. As we will see, the later Byzantines, Nicholas of Methone, Theodore Metochites, and Gregory Palamas, inherit from both of these variants, with certain tendencies toward one pole or the other—and it is in this context that their forms of scepticism should be assessed.³

One of the general themes that comes out of our authors, as will become evident, is that the form of scepticism they employ is couched within a broader methodological discussion on natural reason’s relation to revelation and divine illumination. All agree that revelation is the only source of knowledge, even if held by belief or divine illumination, where certainty is maintained for any set of truths—whether concerning the created world or the divine. As Börje Bydén recognizes correctly, what we see is a kind of dogmatic scepticism, rather than Pyrrhonian (which maintains the abstention from any claims of certain truth), insofar as Byzantine authors still designate a domain of certain knowledge.⁴ This would reflect a variation of a standard Platonic conception of scepticism, where one cannot derive principles of certain knowledge explaining the material world, which exists in flux and instability, from the material world itself: those principles must instead come from causes which transcend the material world—for Plato, the Forms and intellect (νοῦς).⁵ Our Byzantine Christian figures, it would turn out, switch the tables and put philosophy

³ Hence this paper does not focus on the direct influence of ancient Sceptics, particularly like Sextus Empiricus, though certain references are discussed. On the reception of ancient Scepticism in Byzantines, including Sextus, see esp. Bydén (2002), as well as Demetracopoulos (1999) and Lagerlund (2020) 74–76. It is noteworthy that none of our authors countenance the possibility of a third “pole” (as it were), i.e. *no* scepticism—the possibility of strictly certain knowledge obtained through philosophy alone, *apart* from revelation. That one rarely, if at all, finds this kind of position considered in the Byzantine tradition is striking when looking at other traditions—e.g. Avicenna and his successors in the Arabic philosophical tradition who prioritize demonstrative knowledge through reason over revelation (cf. Lagerlund (2020) 65 ff.).

⁴ E.g. in Theodore Metochites, cf. below, n. 64.

⁵ Cf. below, p. 27, nn. 105–106.

and human reason in the position of Plato’s “material world”: reason’s stability and certainty can only be grounded in transcendent truths beyond reason, i.e. divine revelation and illumination.

Background: Early Christian Scepticism and Anti-Scepticism

The sceptical background in Nicholas and later Byzantines is to be found in early Christian and Byzantine figures like Clement of Alexandria and the Cappadocian Fathers (especially Gregory Nazianzen, as we will see), where the latter borrow their argumentative strategies from pagan Sceptical sources—at the same time that they also explicitly *oppose* the Sceptics (both, it would seem, Academic and Pyrrhonian). We should briefly look over Clement and the Cappadocians, inasmuch as they provide a majority of the sceptical context we find in our later Byzantines, along with the way in which they borrow from and transform the arguments of ancient Sceptics.

We find Clement’s position laid out in the *Stromateis*, a loose collection of arguments that defend Christian teaching against Gnostic doctrines, like those of Valentinus and Basilides, alongside false pagan conceptions of true philosophy.⁶ Clement’s general attitude to previous pagan philosophical schools is notably, in his own phrasing, “eclectic” (τὸ ἐκλεκτικόν), as it were a kind of patchwork: he neither rejects—nor accepts—the previous tradition of philosophy wholesale, nor any one school directly (citing Platonists, Aristotelians, Stoics, and Epicureans), but instead maintains that “whatever has been well said by each of those schools which teaches justice along with scientific knowledge of what is sacred—this eclectic whole together is what I call philosophy.”⁷ This goes with Clement’s earlier statement that pagan Greek philosophy and education is sent by God to humanity as a preparation for the full revelation of the *Logos*—correlating with what Clement takes to be “well-said.”⁸ On the flip side, Clement’s emphasis on what is “well-said” as constituting “philosophy” implies its inverse: the remainder leftover from what has been “cut away from human reasonings and re-branded [as divine]” Clement would not claim as “divine”⁹—and hence not true “philosophy.” In this, Clement attempts to strike a *via media*. On the one hand, he follows those like his near-contemporary, Justin Martyr (c. 100–165 CE), in maintaining the harmony of philosophy with Christian revelation.¹⁰ On the other hand, Clement attempts to avoid the destructive pessimism of philosophy’s relation to Christian revelation, cemented in Tertullian’s famous quip,

⁶ On the *Stromateis* and its context, see Karamanolis (2013) 244, Ferguson in Clement of Alexandria, *Stromateis* (1991) 10–19, and Lilla (1971).

⁷ Clement, *Strom.* I.7.37.6, lines 2–4: ἀλλ’ ὅσα εἴρηται παρ’ ἐκάστη τῶν αἰρέσεων τούτων καλῶς, δικαιοσύνην μετὰ εὐσεβοῦς ἐπιστήμης ἐκδιδάσκοντα, τοῦτο σύμπαν τὸ ἐκλεκτικόν φιλοσοφίαν φημί. (Translations my own unless otherwise noted.)

⁸ Clement, *Strom.* I.7.37.1–5. The idea, in turn, is an implicit reference back to Plato, *Timaeus* 47b1–2, who says that philosophy is a gift from God to humanity. For a discussion of Clement’s views of pagan philosophy as ultimately originating in divine revelation, see Lilla (1973) 9–59. As we will later see, in what sense philosophy is such a “gift from God” is disputed between Gregory Palamas and Barlaam: see below, p. 21 and n. 82.

⁹ Clement, *Strom.* I.7.37.6, lines 4–6: ὅσα δὲ ἀνθρωπίνων λογισμῶν ἀποτεμόμενοι παρεχάραξαν, ταῦτα οὐκ ἂν ποτε θεία εἴποιμ’ ἂν. See also Golitsis (2019) 19–20, who reads this passage as meaning that Clement cuts off *all* human reasoning and philosophy from “what is divine”—which is not so apparent, especially in light of Clement’s attempt to show philosophy’s divine origin (see previous note).

¹⁰ See e.g. Justin Martyr, *Dialogue with Trypho* 8.1; cf. Karamanolis (2013) 2–3.

“What has Athens to do with Jerusalem?”¹¹ Yet in maintaining that the divine person of the *Logos*, manifested in the Incarnation, reveals truth in a way philosophy before the *Logos* did not, Clement is necessitated to show in what regard previous philosophical schools did not manifest the truth in the way that the *Logos* did.

An important counterpart is Clement’s claim in *Strom.* VI.7.54.1 that true philosophy, which is concerned with wisdom (σοφία), is a “stable and unchanging apprehension” (κατάληψιν τινα βεβαίαν οὔσαν καὶ ἀμετάπτωτον). Clement’s language directly recalls the Stoic description of apprehension, or “cognitive impression” (κατάληψις), which is stable and fixed in its character.¹² Clement, in this respect, borrows from the Stoic criterion of certainty in knowledge by attaching it directly to his definition of “philosophy,” which is only comprehended in the *Logos*. By possessing knowledge in accordance with the *Logos*, one can adjudicate the truths and falsehoods implicit in other, past philosophical frameworks.¹³ A consequence of this, on the flip side, is that one does *not* possess certain truth in holding knowledge solely in accordance with any one given philosophical school or framework: one is still in need of the *Logos* prior to these frameworks.¹⁴ Clement hence suggests an implicit sceptical stance regarding the position of philosophy by itself, inasmuch as it is a necessary but incomplete part in relation to the greater whole pertaining to the *Logos*: without the containing whole, one lacks the criterion of certainty with philosophy alone.

On the other hand, Clement’s maintenance of a criterion of certainty with the *Logos* means (perhaps paradoxically) that he is concerned to defend against Sceptical critiques of *any* criterion of truth—i.e. Pyrrhonian Sceptics who advocate for the suspension of all judgment. Whereas Academic Sceptics attack the criterion of judgment for the Stoics as leading to certain truth, the

¹¹ See e.g. *De praescriptione haereticorum* 7,3–4, where Tertullian ascribes various heresies to the positions of different philosophical schools—a reason to reject previous philosophical schools, like the Stoics and Platonists. See however Karamanolis (2013) 31–33, who argues that Tertullian yet maintains goodness in human reasoning and philosophy—however almost exclusively identified with Christianity.

¹² See Sextus Empiricus’ testimony of the Stoic position in *Adversus mathematicos* VII.248 (= *Stoicorum veterum fragmenta* II.65), esp.: “A cognitive impression (ἡ κατάληπτική) is one which arises from what is and is stamped and impressed exactly in accordance with what is, of such a kind as could not arise from what is not” (trans. Long-Sedley); Diogenes Laertius, *Vitae philosophorum* VII.54 (= *SVF* II.105): “They [the Stoics] say that the cognitive impression (τὴν κατάληπτικὴν) is the criterion of truth (κριτήριον τῆς ἀληθείας), i.e. the impression arising from what is” (trans. Long-Sedley); see also Zeno in *SVF* I.20, 50.

¹³ See e.g. Clement, *Strom.* I.9.43–44. Cf. Karamanolis (2013) 43; see 121–122 for an elaboration on Clement’s criteria for the specific domains of knowledge in which certainty is possible.

¹⁴ Clement, *Strom.* I.13.57 (esp. 1–2): “Truth, then, is one (μίας τοίνυν οὔσης τῆς ἀληθείας), for error has countless ways of going astray. The philosophical sects, whether Greek or otherwise, are like the Maenads scattering the limbs of Pentheus, each boasting their own limited claim as the whole truth. All things, I believe, are illuminated by the rising of light. So all who stretched out towards the truth, Greeks and non-Greeks alike, could be shown to possess some portion of the Word of Truth—some a considerable part, others a fraction, as it falls out” (trans. Ferguson, modified). See also I.20.97 (esp. 2–4).

Pyrrhonians go one step further and attack *any* criterion of judgment:¹⁵ the acknowledgement of ignorance must eventually rule out even one's claim to know that there is no truth with certainty, and hence any criterion, even of one's own.¹⁶ For someone like Clement who maintains that “philosophy” through the *Logos* gives one a clear, certain criterion of truth, the Sceptics would be a threat, especially in the form of the Pyrrhonians. This provides context for Clement's attack on the Pyrrhonians near the end of the *Stromateis* (Book VIII), where he critiques the suspension of judgment (ἐποχή) as a form of assent, and hence a judgment: even if the Pyrrhonian follows her or his goal of giving assent to the images, for Clement this would mark a judgment—the thing the Pyrrhonian attempts to avoid.¹⁷

This background is important to contextualize in what way Sceptical arguments become used by Clement's Christian contemporaries and successors, especially the Cappadocians who are more influential for the later Byzantines—even when both Clement and other Christians are concerned to defend against the Sceptical project as a whole. As it turns out, the Sceptics become useful for the Christian to indicate the insufficiency of the philosophers outside the criterion of the *Logos*. This brings back Clement's judgment about the parts “cut away” by the philosophers which cannot be so divine and connected to true “philosophy.” Clement does not employ Sceptical arguments to show exactly how the other philosophers fail to attain the truth, yet we find a couple indications that might lead this way: first, he concedes at the end of his attack on the Pyrrhonians that even some in dogmatic schools, or those tending toward dogmatism, are inclined to suspend judgment (ἐποχή) either in matters involving lack of clarity in one's mind or in the subject matter, or also in the arguments themselves.¹⁸ In other words the methods of the Pyrrhonians are still valid, especially where balancing arguments of equal force, for example, whenever the situation obtains, inevitably leads one to suspending judgment. The admission of the frailty of the mind and the potential unclarity in things is mirrored earlier in the *Stromateis* when Clement assesses the philosophical schools as imperfectly attaining to the *Logos* in varying degrees: “Those among the Greeks with the most precise grasp of philosophy discern God both through a reflection (ἔμφασιν) and an adumbration (διάφασιν). Such are the images (φαντασμάτα) of truth our weakness admits, just as you would perceive the things in water—alongside things through transparent and translucent

¹⁵ Karamanolis (2013) 36. On Academic Sceptics, see e.g. Sextus Empiricus, *AM* VII.166–75, esp. where Sextus claims that Carneades, while attempting to prove the “non-existence of the criterion [of truth]” (implicitly for positive dogmatists like the Stoics), himself possesses “a certain criterion”: “both the ‘convincing’ impression (φαντασμάτα) and the one which is simultaneously convincing, undiverted, and thoroughly explored.” On Pyrrhonian Sceptics, see e.g. Diogenes Laertius, *Vitae* IX.78; IX.106–107; Photius, *Bibliotheca* 169b18–170b3 (see next note); and Sextus Empiricus, *PH* I.31–39.

¹⁶ Photius, *Bibliotheca* 169b18–170b3: “Nor indeed, do they [i.e. Pyrrhonian Sceptics] say there is true or false, convincing or unconvincing, existent or non-existent. But the same thing is, it might be said, no more true than false, convincing than unconvincing, or existent than non-existent” (trans. Long-Sedley).

¹⁷ Clement, *Strom.* VIII.5.15–16. As Karamanolis (2013) 127–129 points out, the remaining sections after Clement's initial attack on the Pyrrhonians (VIII.6–9) seem setup as an implicit response to the Sceptics (*n.b.* Book VIII does not have a complete end) by outlining Clement's theory of demonstration. Although he does not explicitly state his purpose for discussing demonstration in these remaining sections, Clement seems to be showing how knowledge of universals in relation to particulars, as the content of demonstration, does make possible scientific knowledge—a positive counter-reply to the Pyrrhonian claim he has just critiqued.

¹⁸ Clement, *Strom.* VIII.5.16.3. Cf. discussion of the exception Clement allows for suspension of judgment (ἐποχή) for the dogmatist still lacking clarity in Havrda (2016) 215–218 and Veres (2019).

bodies—as an image.”¹⁹ On the one hand, the thrust of Clement’s statement is supposed to show in a positive way how the philosophers can lead one to the full truth found in the *Logos*. On the other hand, Clement’s language of perceiving “things in water” like an “image” (φαντασία) is a striking juxtaposition to the earlier language of the “stable and unchanging apprehension (κατάληψιν)” — often spoken in the context of an “image” or “impression” communicated to the mind: what is associated with the *Logos*.

The lack of stability and unchangeable character found in previous philosophies, although understated in Clement, becomes emphasized in other, later Christian authors, where we find the use of Sceptical language employed. An example of this can be seen in Ps.-Justin’s *Exhortation to the Greeks*, when he points out that disagreement between Plato and Aristotle directly implies their “ignorance,” implicitly a failure in attaining the truth.²⁰ The strategy of showing disagreement between philosophical schools can also be found in the Pyrrhonian “mode of dispute,” discussed among the other “Five Modes” involved in suspension of judgment, according to which the mutual disagreement between philosophers on a given position leads to such suspension.²¹ One example that the Pyrrhonian Sceptic, Sextus Empiricus, cites is on the very issue of the criterion of truth: “Some have asserted that there is one (e.g. the Stoics and certain others), some that there is not (among them, Xenias of Corinth, and Xenophanes of Colophon who says: ‘but belief is found over all’); and we suspend judgment (ἐπέσχομεν) as to whether there is one or not.”²² One can see this as an extension of the standard Pyrrhonian principle of balancing arguments of equal weight with each other, where the dispute between schools *de facto* is grounds for suspending clear judgment in any direction. For Christians like Ps.-Justin, while similarly agreeing on the impossibility of ascertaining certain truth within the periphery of the schools, they instead see it as pointing to the *Logos* beyond that periphery. Hence the suspension of judgment from the first “mode of dispute” becomes a tool, rather than the end in itself.

This helps provide the background to what we find in the Cappadocian Fathers of the fourth century CE, especially in Gregory Nazianzen who becomes one main influence for the form of scepticism we find in Theodore Metochites and Gregory Palamas. One of the primary factors behind the Cappadocians’ sceptical arguments concerning reason was the Eunomian Controversy, where Eunomius of Cyzicus and his followers claimed that the Son (as the *Logos*, i.e. the second Trinitarian person) is “unlike” (ἀνόμοιον) in substance from the Father, in contrast to the orthodox position which maintained that the Father and Son are of the *same* substance (ὁμοούσιος). For the Eunomians, the Father (as God) is characterized as “ingenerate,” while the Son, as produced from the Father, is characterized as “generated”: if the Son were ascribed as God, this would mean that “God” implies two attributes—“ingenerate” and “generated”—resulting in composition, rather than simplicity, in the substance of God. One key premise in the Eunomians’ claims was that predicates applied to God directly correspond to the substance (οὐσία) of God—which further

¹⁹ Clement, *Strom.* I.19.94.7; trans. Ferguson, modified. The juxtaposition of “reflection” and “adumbration,” especially in this context, is paralleled in Plutarch’s *Moralia* 354c1 and 417c1, both referring to contexts of truths veiled in religious symbols, which Clement may be hearkening back to. Special thanks to an anonymous reviewer for this reference.

²⁰ Ps.-Justin, *Exhortation* 5.1. Cf. Karamanolis (2013) 35.

²¹ Sextus Empiricus, *PH* I.164–169.

²² Sextus Empiricus, *PH* II.18; trans. Morison, modified.

implies that the essence of God could be directly grasped by the human intellect.²³ Hence, one of the main ways in which Cappadocians like Gregory Nazianzen and Basil of Caesarea attacked the Eunomians was in radically questioning whether the human intellect could apprehend with certainty the essence of *any* entity—whether created or (especially) uncreated.

We can see this stricter form of scepticism in Gregory Nazianzen's *Oration* 28, where Gregory sets out the nature of theology concerning God, or the *Logos* (as in Clement): theology must inevitably lead one to apophaticism in any discourse, mirroring the nature of God who transcends all finite distinctions and is purely infinite—"like an undefined, unlimited ocean of being."²⁴ The attempt to comprehend God in rational discourse is bound to fail: as Gregory points out in 28.4, discourse (λόγος) can only dimly indicate God's existence and nature, if at all, whereas the human intellect's comprehension (περιλαβείν) of God is impossible by its own nature.²⁵ The failure is not just due to the infinite nature of the intellect's object, God, but more the limited nature of the intellect in itself. Implicit in the passage is a corollated scepticism of Greek philosophy's claim for the possibility of attaining knowledge of God's nature, even if such description is difficult.

Gregory makes this notion explicit later when he expands the limitation of the intellect's comprehension to knowledge of other, intelligible aspects of reality—not just God:

“All truth and all reasoning, then, is both obscure and hard to trace out. It is as if we employ a small tool on big constructions, insofar as we use human wisdom in the hunt for knowledge of beings (τὴν τῶν ὄντων γνῶσιν): we attend to [supra-sensible] intelligible realities (τοῖς νοητοῖς) with the senses, i.e. not without the senses. By these same senses we are perplexed and led astray, and we cannot get nearer the truth by meeting things in their naked reality with naked intellect. Our intellect cannot receive impressions by direct, certain apprehension (κατάληψιν).” (*Oration* 28.21, 1–7)

One observation we can make here is Gregory's use of the word, κατάληψις, “direct apprehension,” which we saw above in Clement. This directly recalls the anti-Stoic context of the Sceptics in their critique of the certainty of knowledge obtained through impressions made in the intellect, and hence the latter's “apprehension” of its objects. In Clement we saw his positive appropriation of the “stable and unchanging apprehension” which pertains to true “philosophy” correlating with the *Logos*. Here we see the inverse in Gregory: the intellect's grasp of things “in their naked reality”

²³ On the history of the Eunomian controversy, and the Cappadocians' critical response to their framework, see Radde-Gallwitz (2009) (esp. 96–112 on the background to Eunomius) and DelCogliano (2010).

²⁴ Gregory Nazianzen, *Oration* 38.36 (PG:36, 317, 26–27): οἶόν τι πέλαγος οὐσίας ἄπειρον καὶ ἀόριστον. The phrase becomes a significant metaphysical characterization in the later Byzantine theologian, John of Damascus, and in the Latin tradition in Duns Scotus' characterization of God as pure infinity, rather than pure being, as in Thomas Aquinas: on this see Cross (1999) 39 ff.

²⁵ Gregory Nazianzen, *Oration* 28.4, esp. 5–12. Earlier in lines 1–4, Gregory references an unnamed Greek philosopher who, in his words, claims that to “know” (νοῆσαι) God is difficult, while speaking (φράσαι) of God is impossible—which, as we see, Gregory inverts the order, i.e. *to speak* of God difficult, *to know* impossible. Various commentators have pointed to Plato's *Timaeus* 28c, where the latter claims that “to find the maker and father of this universe is difficult,” while “to declare to all” the maker and father is impossible (28c3–5). Gregory's version of the unnamed philosopher's phrase as “to know” rather than “to find” is striking in this respect, and more so his aim to show that knowing is impossible. See Norris (1991) 110 for further discussion of this passage.

reaches an impasse. In one sense this runs contrary to Clement’s claim that we do, in fact, possess certainty in grasping the *Logos* as the content of true “philosophy.” Although Clement’s criterion excludes knowledge obtained solely in any given philosophical school—what perhaps correlates here with Gregory’s “knowledge of reality”—one might think that Gregory would concede that theology in light of the *Logos* does give us such certainty.

Yet even here, Gregory seems to part ways from Clement when he goes on to claim that theology, or “the account concerning God (ὁ περὶ Θεοῦ λόγος), insofar as it is more perfect, is also more difficult to attain, since it contains more counter-arguments and solutions which are more laborious” (28.21, 7–9). The language of “counter-arguments” (ἀντιλήψεις) is once again striking, inasmuch as it calls to mind the Sceptics’ method of juxtaposing arguments of equal weight for and against a given position—what Gregory suggests with theology.²⁶ The parallel goes further later in the treatise when Gregory goes on to show the fruitlessness of the philosopher’s efforts to uncover the causes behind various natural phenomena: the philosopher is “wholly earthbound or terrestrial, ignorant of [his] very ignorance” (28.28, 37–38), unless he comes to realize by his reason (λόγος) things that surpass his reason.²⁷ This does not mean, for Gregory, that reason cannot determine the existence, i.e. *that*, something is: it is rather when reason attempts to reflect on the causes of that thing, i.e. *what* it is, that it must end up realizing its failure to grasp that thing’s essence.²⁸

With his phrasing of reason realizing its ignorance, Gregory seems to affirm the same aim of the Pyrrhonians in philosophy, or at least a very similar one: the goal of reasoning is to make one realize one’s ignorance and hence, rather than attempt to solve the impasse by reason, to suspend reason, or judgment. Where this would lead the Pyrrhonian to live by the appearances, Gregory would agree in an analogous sense: for the enlightened Christian, the realization of reason’s ignorance should lead one to live in accordance with faith (πίστις). One can also see the contrast to the Pyrrhonian in this, where faith (πίστις), for Gregory, means positive knowledge as a sure guide to truth: by contrast, the Pyrrhonian would deny *any* such guide or criterion.²⁹

On comparing Gregory’s account with Clement, one finds concurrence as well as sharp contrasts. Gregory’s “earthbound” philosopher finds a parallel in Clement’s view that the pagan philosophical schools made emendations to “true philosophy” from the *Logos*: as abiding solely in their domain, outside of the *Logos*, the pagan philosophers are unable to possess certain knowledge about either reality or the Creator. Where one finds a contrast is in Gregory’s emphasis on the discontinuity

²⁶ Cf. Demetracopoulos (1999) 137–146, who argues that Gregory drew directly from Sextus Empiricus’ *Pyrrhoniae hypotyposes* for *Orations* 28 and 29. Gregory also makes the explicit claim that all arguments imply their opposites, similarly to the Pyrrhonian position: see *Carmina moralia*, PG:37, 750A–751A; cf. below, pp. 16–17.

²⁷ Gregory Nazianzen, *Oration* 28.28, 26–38.

²⁸ See Gregory Nazianzen, *Oration* 28.5, where Gregory clarifies that his statements on the limitation of reason’s grasp of the first cause (i.e. God) apply to *what* the cause is (ἥτις ἐστίν), not *that* it is (οὐχ ὅτι ἔσται): a *fortiori* Gregory’s sceptical claims lie with comprehensive knowledge of things, particularly in their essence/substance (οὐσία), rather than in their existence.

²⁹ Gregory Nazianzen, *Oration* 28.28, 35. Even here, the difference between Gregory and the Pyrrhonian position (as in Sextus Empiricus) on religious dogmatic claims may not be so great: see Veres (2020), who argues that Sextus’ criteria for Sceptical examination is narrower in the case religious beliefs, allowing for the Pyrrhonian to engage in ordinary religious practices regardless of whether the general cultural, religious context requires holding to dogmatic beliefs.

between reason (λόγος) and faith (πίστις). Gregory seems to emphasize that knowledge derived from faith cannot be found, even if partially, in knowledge derived from reason. By contrast, Clement seems to emphasize that knowledge is of the same kind between the domain of philosophy, as found in the pagan schools, and the domain of faith (πίστις)—i.e. “true philosophy.” In other words, Clement’s claim against pagan philosophy attaining truth results from incomplete principles, not an incapacity of reason itself: the philosophical schools possess *certain*, correct principles in some degree, as “parts,” but none possesses the *whole* correct set.³⁰ Reason is then hindered merely in not *yet* possessing correct principles. By contrast, Gregory implicitly argues against this conception when he claims that reason is inherently incapable of possessing principles of true knowledge through itself. It is then no accident that pagan philosophical schools do not possess any true principles, because reason in itself cannot provide the means to attain the truth. Hence, Gregory’s scepticism suggests a greater disjunct between reason and faith in a way not found in Clement.³¹

This background should give us the context to adjudicate the differing positions we find developed in later Byzantines of the 12th to 14th centuries CE. The two positions we find in Clement of Alexandria and Gregory Nazianzen hence form two “poles” between which our later Byzantine authors situate themselves:

1. “Mild” scepticism: “stable and unchanging apprehension” (κατάληψις) of reality by reason is possible, albeit only when such knowledge accords with Christian revelation: i.e. reason has the ability to comprehend reality by its own means, yet imperfectly without reference to principles manifested by faith and/or divine illumination.
2. “Strict” scepticism: “stable and unchanging apprehension” of reality by reason is not possible: i.e. reason cannot comprehend reality by its own means—instead principles concerning reality and God can only be communicated by faith (πίστις) and/or by divine illumination.

In position (1), the kind of sceptical argument we see would be analogous to an Academic Sceptic who critiques a specific criterion of truth, like that of the Stoics: so the same, as we saw in Clement, against the criteria of the differing schools as possessing the truth of the *Logos* incompletely; one may still have access to the truth, in some sense, in the domain of philosophy. In position (2), by contrast, access to the truth is not possible in the domain of philosophy, inasmuch as it is outside what is communicated by faith (πίστις) rather than by reason (λόγος). This would be closer to a Pyrrhonian Sceptical position which suggests reason’s incapability to settle on any criterion of truth: although, as we saw above in Gregory, the domain of faith and revelation still implies a criterion of certainty (unlike the Pyrrhonian position questioning any given criterion).

As we will see in the next sections, the three later figures of Nicholas of Methone, Theodore Metochites, and Gregory Palamas each alternate between these two positions with certain variances:

³⁰ Cf. above n. 14.

³¹ Other contemporaries of Gregory, like Gregory of Nyssa and Basil of Caesarea (e.g. *Contra Eunomium* I–II), draw a loosely similar approach to what we have seen, with the emphasis on the limitedness of reason, and thus philosophy’s inability to comprehend reality: see Karamanolis (2013) 33–34.

- In the case of Nicholas, while responding against contemporaries of his who equate philosophy (focusing especially on Proclus) with truths revealed in revelation, Nicholas ends up maintaining a position closer to that of Clement (i.e. [1]): that Proclus incompletely understands “true” philosophy as divinely illuminated and manifested in the writings of Pseudo-Dionysius. Hence Nicholas’ sceptical critiques of Proclus and his supporters only address the faulty criteria held by them.
- Theodore ends up adopting position (2) when he explicitly attributes the Pyrrhonian Sceptics’ position to Gregory Nazianzen: hence he approves of the Pyrrhonians’ general approach in opposing arguments as leading to suspending judgment. Yet Theodore still maintains that certainty can be found in divine revelation (ultimately agreeing with Gregory).
- Palamas adjudicates between positions (1) and (2): on the one hand, in responding to his opponent, Barlaam, who uses Clement’s premise to maintain the equality of truth in both philosophy and revelation, Palamas claims that philosophy cannot attain certainty from its own ground (thus [2]). At the same time, Palamas affirms that divine illumination, in the domain of grace, grants epistemic certainty to the first premises of theology as a discursive science—hence, in some sense, abiding by (1).

Nicholas of Methone: Asserting the Stability of Divine Philosophy over Pagan Philosophy

The context for Nicholas’ critiques of Proclus, alongside his sceptical remarks on the nature of reason outside the domain of divine illumination, comes out of his treatise, the *Refutation of Proclus’ Elements of Theology*, a polemical commentary that covers 198 of the total 211 propositions in Proclus’ *Elements*. Nicholas’ stated aim in the Preface of the *Refutation* is to correct the errors of certain, unnamed contemporaries or near-contemporaries of his who have “partaken of pagan learning (ἔξω παιδείας) [...] despising the clarity, simplicity, and uncontrived quality of [the divine mysteries]” (1, 19–21)—and in this, advocated the philosophical framework of Proclus. Yet in advocating for “pagan learning,” as Proclus best represents, Nicholas claims that these contemporaries have ended up in “blasphemous heresies.”

To whom Nicholas is responding in this later passage has long puzzled scholars. Nicholas does not name his opponents or give a good indication who they would be. The last known extant discussions of Proclus (among other Platonists) prior to Nicholas are from Michael Psellos (1017/8–1096 CE) and Psellos’ student, John Italos (c. 1025–after 1082 CE), both roughly 60–80 years before Nicholas wrote the *Refutation*. Various scholars have theorized that Nicholas must be responding to Psellos,³² even though on closer inspection, Psellos in various cases parallels Nicholas’ approach

³² See e.g. Podskalsky (1976).

—and there seems to be little evidence for any lack of Christian orthodoxy in Psellos.³³ Still, there are certain, insightful passages in Psellos to which Nicholas appears to be responding (whether directly or mediated in contemporaries of his). For example, in a commentary on Proposition 35 from Proclus' *Elements of Theology*, Psellos states that, although Christian theological teaching on the Trinity does not necessitate proofs, “among the wise Greeks, reason (λόγος) is a highly productive component of their theological proofs, and it also contributes no small part to our own discourse as regards the union and distinction of the Son in relation to the Father.”³⁴ Psellos here, and in other passages, seems to mirror the approach we saw in Clement, where philosophy attains a portion of the complete truth contained in the revealed *Logos* (i.e. the Incarnation). Reason (λόγος, lowercase) does, then, give us access, even if impartially, to fundamental truths pertaining to God and reality.³⁵

It is this kind of position in Psellos that Nicholas appears to attack in stark terms in the *Refutation's* Preface, when he compares the efforts of Proclus, among others of “outside,” or pagan, wisdom (ἔξω σοφίαν), as attempting to build another Tower of Babel:

In this [Proclus] baked as bricks cogitations kneaded together and mixed from every Hellenic teaching, and arranging [these cogitations] into 211 chapters, placing one on top of the other, he raised up a tower using the continuity (ἀλληλουχία) of logical demonstrations instead of mortar. Through such a construction he aimed not only to reach to heaven, but even to surpass the super-celestial intellects in knowledge and to run up to God himself, the principle of all things, and to grasp the ungraspable (τὸν ἀκατάληπτον καταλαμβάνειν).³⁶

Nicholas' emphasis here is strong: reason, in the form of “logical demonstrations” put together in Proclus' 211 propositions of the *Elements*, attempts to grasp what is ungraspable (ἀκατάληπτον) by its own nature, and hence necessarily fails. Proclus is symbolic of “reason” within the domain of past Greek philosophers, and forms the pinnacle of previous thought inasmuch as he systematizes “Hellenic teaching” in the *Elements'* propositions—hence the comparison to the “Tower of Babel,” in Nicholas' construal, in the false thinking that reason could lead one to God. The use of καταλαμβάνειν, “to grasp,” in this passage is striking when we look back to Gregory Nazianzen, where Gregory also denied the possibility for stable, certain apprehension (καταλήψεσιν) in the case of God—alongside all beings in general. This seems to underscore Nicholas' point all the

³³ Among various examples, see for instance Psellos' comment from *Philosophica Minora* II.35, 119,4–13, on Proclus' *Elements of Theology*, Prop. 81, where Psellos partially accepts Proclus' claim of an “inseparable power,” in a metaphorical sense—for instance, John the Baptist as a forerunner of Christ, and hence an illumination, or “power,” proceeding from Christ as the first cause—yet Psellos rejects the literal notion of “an intermediary between soul and body” as not concurring with Christian “discourse.” This mirrors Nicholas' discriminative approach in certain of Proclus' propositions, as we will see. For a full discussion and comparison of Michael Psellos alongside Nicholas of Methone on Proclus' *Elements*, see Robinson (Forthcoming).

³⁴ Michael Psellos, *PM* II.35, 117,24–118,4; trans. Robinson.

³⁵ On Psellos' “rationalism” in this sense, see e.g. his *Letter to Xiphilinos* (cf. Kaldellis and Polemis (2015) 163–176), where Psellos defends and argues for the harmony of philosophizing with Plato and other ancient philosophers in doing theology with the divinely inspired Church Fathers (special thanks to the suggestion of an anonymous reviewer); cf. Panagopoulos (2014) and Robinson (Forthcoming).

³⁶ Nicholas of Methone, *Refutation of Proclus' Elements of Theology* 3,22–29; trans. Robinson, modified.

more: not simply that Proclus' knowledge was incomplete, as Psellos would maintain, but rather impossible.

Just how Proclus and “pagan wisdom” fail to attain truths corresponding to God and the principles of reality becomes clearer when we look at Nicholas' description of his contemporaries: for Nicholas, they trade out the “clarity” (σαφές), “simplicity,” and “uncontrived quality” (ἀκατάσκευον), belonging to the divine grace and mysteries of the Christian faith, with what is “complex” (ποικίλον), “enigmatic” (γρίφον), and “clever” (κομψόν).³⁷ On the one hand the characterization is straightforwardly descriptive of sophistry, inasmuch as the sophist's words have the appearance of “enigma” and being “clever,” suggesting truths about reality that are otherwise.³⁸ Yet the juxtaposition of the latter with the nature of the divine mysteries as “clear,” “simple,” and “uncontrived” also suggests that knowledge imparted through the latter is of a more certain character compared to what is “complex” in pagan wisdom. This again recalls Clement of Alexandria's characterization of the content of “true philosophy” as “stable” and “secure,” closely following Nicholas' characterization of divine wisdom as “clear” and “simple.” In this sense, Nicholas adheres to the sense of certainty we find in Clement's notion of “true philosophy” (and similarly in Psellos as well).

At the same time it is also clear in Nicholas that reason in itself, apart from divine illumination, does not have access to the truth: any connection that reason does have to truth is only in virtue of confirmation from divine revelation, or from those who have received divine illumination in accordance with revelation—as for example the writings of “St. Dionysius the Areopagite” (i.e. the Pseudo-Dionysius) on which Nicholas often relies throughout the treatise. This comes out later in the Preface when Nicholas begins his treatise, “neither confident in my own wisdom nor ambitious to display the worldly wisdom (σοφία...οἰκεία) that I have acquired from human teaching (for I am not unaware that I am subject to ignorance both from natural weakness and sluggishness of mind).”³⁹ Nicholas' methodology is telling: on the one hand he accepts the validity of “worldly wisdom” (οἰκεία σοφία), yet he concedes his ignorance from the “natural weakness” of his mind—and instead invokes the *Logos* (as God), and all revelation pertaining to the *Logos*, in speaking of truth that cannot be communicated through human reason alone.

How Nicholas understands the imperfectness of human knowledge becomes apparent in his commentary on the *Elements*' Prop. 82, where Proclus proves that a bodiless entity which is “capable of reverting toward itself” (πρὸς ἑαυτὸ ἐπιστρεπτικὸν ὄν) will be participated separately.⁴⁰ Proclus' proof mainly deals with cases like the soul's relation to a living body: as immaterial, and to the degree that its activity does not depend on its respective body (e.g. in thinking), it is “separately participated,” while to the degree it depends on its participating body (e.g. in biological functions, like growth, or sensation, and so on), its activity goes outside itself and does not revert back to itself—hence not “separately” participated.⁴¹

³⁷ Nicholas of Methone, *Refutation* 1,8–2,12.

³⁸ Robinson (2017) 90.

³⁹ Nicholas of Methone, *Refutation* 2,13–17; trans. Robinson.

⁴⁰ See Proclus, *ET* Prop. 82, 76,22–23; see also Dodds' commentary in Proclus' *Elements* (1963) 244.

⁴¹ Cf. Proclus, *ET* Prop. 80.

In his commentary, Nicholas ends up relating the language of participation from the passage to the soul with its body: contrary to Proclus, Nicholas maintains a partial Aristotelian stance that the soul (and its corresponding intellect) is inseparable from its body insofar as it “does not live nor the intellect understand without the body conjoined to them.”⁴² Yet Nicholas goes on to maintain that the soul’s inseparability from the body is connected with its state of imperfect knowledge, even though at the end of the commentary, Nicholas states that it is possible for the soul to be “separated perfectly” while still being ontologically present in (or related to) the body.⁴³ Of relevance for us is the way that Nicholas concurs with Proclus on the nature of knowledge necessitating the soul’s “perfect separation,” yet Nicholas parts ways with Proclus by claiming that the soul, in its current postlapsarian state, is *not* so truly separate: in man’s separation from God through Adam’s disobedience, Nicholas takes the Genesis account of the Fall seriously and understands the soul’s lack of true separation from the body as one consequence in this light. Hence the rejoinder in the passage, and throughout, of revelation through faith providing the only certain path to truth—even though it does not qualify as complete knowledge, as Nicholas acknowledges.⁴⁴

So far all this suggests that Nicholas’ scepticism about human reason lies somewhere between the two poles of scepticism sketched above. On the one hand, Nicholas indicates that the knowledge obtained in philosophy—paradigmatically represented in Proclus—is “complex” and prone to ignorance and error: certainty can only be found in what is communicated in revelation by faith (thus, position [2]). On the other hand, Nicholas does seem to affirm that “partial” knowledge is possible, as we saw in his consideration of knowledge from Proclus’ premises: knowledge pertaining to truths, even if “ungraspable,” is possible only in virtue of divine revelation, or those so inspired by revelation (thus, position [1]).

The latter implicitly hearkens back to Clement’s view that specific philosophical schools only managed to understand truths incompletely, without the *Logos*’ manifestation. Nicholas’ trend this

⁴² Nicholas of Methone, *Refutation* 84,24–29: “For although the soul and its intellect are incorporeal and self-revertive (ἐπιστρέπτικά), nevertheless so long as they are in bodies they act with the bodies, and the soul does not live nor the intellect understand without the body conjoined to them. But whenever they are separated in substance, then they also have a separate activity” (trans. Robinson). The last sentence shows where Nicholas parts ways with Aristotle, who, by contrast, maintains the inseparability of the soul and its body (cf. *De Anima* II.1, 413a3–7)—with the exception of the active intellect (*De Anima* III.5, 430a22–25): hence the soul (except the intellect) dies with the body for Aristotle, while for Nicholas the soul maintains its separate being and activity apart from the now-dead body.

⁴³ Nicholas of Methone, *Refutation* 85,17–24: “Certainly the soul is not now perfectly separate from the body conjoined to it, nor is its intellect [perfectly separate], and so it neither perfectly lives nor perfectly intellects, even though it is intellective and immortal in its own nature, and furnishes life to the body from itself. It is able to revert perfectly to itself whenever it is separated perfectly or whenever it will also dispose the participating [body] according to itself, as our argument already made clear sufficiently. The [soul] by its activity will be separate when [its] substance is separated as well” (trans. Robinson, modified). I take it that Nicholas’ claim of the soul “disposing” the body “according to itself” indicates the soul’s mode of being, or activity, as not subjected to passions belonging to the body—despite its embodied existence.

⁴⁴ Nicholas of Methone, *Refutation* 84,29–85,5.

way is reflected, for instance, in his approval and reliance on “Dionysius”⁴⁵ in correcting Proclus. Nicholas claims, as was common in earlier Byzantine thought, that Proclus took his material from Ps.-Dionysius, and either modified it in an un-Christian, impious way or, even when “preserving” the same content, simply stole from “Dionysius” and applied the latter’s teachings in a polytheistic context.⁴⁶ This suggests that the degree to which “philosophy,” while pagan and outside revelation, is true can only be in virtue of its implicit reliance on a more authoritative source, which encompasses the same content that is communicated (to the degree it is true): this certainly seems to come close to the conception of philosophy from Clement (i.e. position [1], above). As we will see below, Nicholas’ position comes close to Palamas, although Palamas more strongly distinguishes the domain of reason from faith.

Theodore Metochites: Affirming the Harmony of the Pyrrhonians and the Faith

Theodore Metochites stands as somewhat of a contrast to Nicholas of Methone, coming just over 100 years after Nicholas. Whereas Nicholas offered up his sceptical critique as a way of defending the truth of divine revelation—namely in recognizing the falsehood of “pagan wisdom,” represented in Proclus, diverting from this path—Theodore is strikingly disconnected from this context. At the outset, Theodore’s shift into a sceptical position seems to be motivated from purely philosophical concerns, particularly in the nature of the natural world.⁴⁷ Part of this may also reflect Theodore’s status: whereas Nicholas wrote as bishop of Methone, Theodore wrote as a polymath, employed in Andronicus II Palaeologus’ court, hence not in a position to defend Christian teaching publicly.⁴⁸ Among other works, Theodore wrote three major philosophical treatises: the *Stoicheiosis Astronomike* (“Elements of Astronomy”), the *Paraphrases of Aristotle’s Writings on Natural Philosophy*, and, relevant for us, the *Semeioseis Gnomikai* (“Sententious Notes”), a collection of varying historical and philosophical essays.⁴⁹

It is especially in the latter work that we find Theodore set out his views on knowledge and what can or cannot be attained with certainty. In treaties like *Semeioseis* 22 and 23, Theodore concludes that mathematical knowledge does not entail disagreements in the way that knowledge does in

⁴⁵ For instance, often cited as “divine and great in divine things” (ὁ θεῖος καὶ τὰ θεῖα πολλὸς Διονύσιος) (Nicholas of Methone, *Refutation* 79,10–11), suggesting that Ps.-Dionysius (with the label as “divine”) possesses the criterion of certain truth.

⁴⁶ See e.g. Nicholas of Methone, *Refutation* 117,23–29. It is notable that, even in this context, Nicholas approves of Proclus’ proposition (*ET Prop.* 122), on the maintenance of the gods’ (or God’s) transcendence in providence—his only disapproval is in the application of the proposition to multiple gods rather than one God. This provides a noteworthy example of the critique of “partial knowledge” applied to Proclus: the error committed by Proclus is only in “distorting” the true content communicated from Dionysius, who was illumined and thus possessed certainty through faith.

⁴⁷ For a thorough investigation of Theodore Metochites’ scepticism and his sources, see Bydén (2002).

⁴⁸ As it is, one could speculate about Metochites’ changing fortunes influencing his sceptical views, considering his father George Metochites’ exile and imprisonment under Andronicus II, and Metochites’ own exile after Andronicus III’s victory in the civil war of 1328 CE (although it would seem the *Semeioseis* were written in 1326). On Metochites’ life, see Bydén (2011).

⁴⁹ Bydén (2020) 1866–1867.

the natural world, especially the domain of philosophy.⁵⁰ This sets the context for what Theodore goes on to claim in *Semeiosis* 61, that the Sceptics’⁵¹ “opposition to the claim that anything can be understood is not entirely without reason.”⁵² On the one hand, one can see in these texts that Theodore presents a strong yet unique view of scepticism based on both the nature of the subject matter under study by philosophers (esp. in *Sem.* 22–23), and by the philosophers even by the nature of their own argumentation (esp. in *Sem.* 61). Yet as one may also recognize, how Theodore maintains the latter claim—i.e. the denial of the “comprehension of all things” (πάσαν κατάληψιν)—with his claim that mathematics can be known with certainty is not immediately apparent. It will be worth comparing the two sets of texts to get a better sense of Theodore’s scepticism.

In *Semeiosis* 22, Theodore begins by observing a “striking lack of dissension among the philosophers who are mathematicians,” even though he concedes some are “more or less expert in this discipline than others” from their writings left behind.⁵³ However the variability counts little in Theodore’s estimation. Even between past Greeks among themselves or in contrast to other non-Greeks, and non-Greeks among themselves as well—cases which conceivably would involve natural “conflict” between different, separate cultures—Theodore maintains: “In the science of mathematics, and on a given problem or subject of investigation, there are no contradiction or irreconcilable ideas at all in mathematics, any more than a man is in opposition to himself.”⁵⁴ Theodore expands this notion when he considers that “all people, shooting from different places or different languages, since they are looking at the same goal, all of them hit the same spot and are successful, whoever they may be”: in other words everyone has direct, unmediated, and certain access to mathematical objects outside the apparent variances of language, mental agility, cultural differences, and so on.⁵⁵ Theodore connects this state of concord for the mathematical philosophers to the ontological state of their subject matter—namely its “stability” (τὸ βεβηκός) and “simplicity” (ἀπλοϊκόν). This provides us the criteria for certain knowledge, and where it is hence lacking, for example in natural things:

For concerning that which is one and always the same and never changes in any way whatsoever, in accordance with any argument, thing, or accident, the correct apprehension (κατάληψις) is also altogether identical and not by its nature at all ambiguous, as is hence the case with things which are in nature and subject to coming-to-

⁵⁰ See Theodore Metochites, *Semeiosis* 22 (“On the lack of dissension in the science of mathematics”) and 23 (“On instability in natural science”).

⁵¹ Or literally “those who practice withholding assent” (τῶν ἐφεκτικῶν).

⁵² Theodore Metochites, *Sem.* 61, 4,3–4: “Ὅτι οὐκ ἔξω λόγου παντάπασι δόξειεν ἂν εἶναι τὰ τῶν ἐφεκτικῶν ἐναντιουμένων πρὸς πᾶσαν κατάληψιν, καὶ ὅτι Πλάτων καὶ Σωκράτης ἀρχὰς εἰς τοῦτ’ ἔδωκαν.

⁵³ Theodore Metochites, *Sem.* 22, 194,26–31.

⁵⁴ Theodore Metochites, *Sem.* 22, 196,8–11; trans. Hult.

⁵⁵ Theodore Metochites, *Sem.* 22, 196,15–24; trans. Hult. Intriguingly Theodore ends up connecting this state of certainty to peace (εἰρήνη) and the lack of factions (ἀσασίαστος), such that all humans would endure in this state if their affairs were in accord with the stability of mathematics’ domain (196,27–198,8). This certainly comes close to the Sceptics’ goal of suspending all judgment (ἐποχή) in all inquiries of knowledge. Furthermore, one modern echo of Metochites on mathematics is in David Hume’s *Enquiry Concerning Human Understanding*, where Hume includes mathematics, as an example of the “relations of ideas,” which escapes the domain of sceptical doubt in contrast to “matters of fact” (such as whether the sun will rise each day): cf. Lagerlund (2020) 147 ff.

be (ὑπὸ γένεσιν) and, since they constantly flow and change into their opposites, force the accounts (λόγους) of them to change with them and enable the existence of opposite views.⁵⁶

A number of striking features come out from Theodore's definition. First, we may see why he thinks mathematics provides the requisite stability that other sciences or disciplines do not: the objects of mathematics remain exactly the same across all variable dimensions, as we saw above. By contrast, things by "nature" and which "come to be" (γένεσις) necessarily imply changeability and instability. Theodore's inference that the "accounts" change with their subject matter (ὑποκείμενον) explains why he thinks mathematics is "stable," following its objects—and why all other disciplines essentially connected to the natural world, in any whichever way, are prone to instability (as we will next see).

One other striking similarity in the passage is Theodore's definition of correct apprehension (κατάληψις) closely paralleling Clement's definition of "true philosophy" as a "stable, unchanging apprehension" (κατάληψιν τινα βεβαίαν οὔσαν καὶ ἀμετάπτωτον). Whereas Clement identifies this with the *Logos*, i.e. God in virtue of the Incarnation, Theodore attaches this to mathematics—something perceived directly and naturally by all people. In some ways this comes as a contrast to all the previous authors we have seen who attach certainty to God—whether as the culmination of philosophy (as Clement), or simply in divine revelation, apart from philosophy (as in Gregory Nazianzen): in these previous, varying cases, they would maintain that divine revelation is necessary for the criteria of certainty, even in cases more supportive of philosophy, like Clement. By contrast Theodore seems to affirm that one *can* have certain knowledge from the created world—albeit, strictly within mathematics—outside revelation. Or at least so it would seem.

Given this, Theodore's explicit affirmation of the Pyrrhonian Sceptics in *Semeiosis* 61 is a paradoxical contrast to his strong claim about mathematics. Theodore begins the treatise as an explication on the phrase, "To every argument there is counter-argument" (λόγῳ παντὶ λόγος παλαίει). The phrase itself goes back at least to Gregory Nazianzen's *Carmina Moralia*, where Gregory claims, "Reasonings count for little toward the knowledge of God: for every argument is opposed to another argument" (οἱ μὲν λογισμοὶ μικρὸν εἰς γνῶσιν Θεοῦ / λόγῳ γάρ ἐστι πᾶς λόγος ἀντίστατος).⁵⁷ In this respect Theodore implicitly takes up the sceptical character of Gregory Nazianzen, from passages like *Oration* 28 (as we saw above), and explicitly connects it to the Sceptics' position:

For it is indeed obvious that much of that which is said by the Sceptics is not inappropriate; and many matters are by their very nature ambiguous and give space to opposite opinions and arguments; and therefore it is very easy to attack them vigorously and express serious disbelief, not to say distrust, of one interpretation of a matter as well as of its opposite. And even if one interpretation is accepted as true, it is possible to feel unsatisfied and unsure and at a loss because of the arguments of the opposite side; and

⁵⁶ Theodore Metochites, *Sem.* 22, 198,12–18; trans. Hult, modified.

⁵⁷ Gregory Nazianzen, *Carmina moralia*, PG:37, 750A–751A. Cf. above, pp. 6–8.

then a great lack of faith and certainty (βεβαιότητα), and a condition (διάθεσις) of ignorance and non-comprehension (ἀκαταληψίας) prevailing by necessity.⁵⁸

Initially Theodore appears to go further than the early Christian use of the first of the Pyrrhonians' Five Modes, namely in juxtaposing the positions of the philosophical, dogmatic schools that use opposing arguments:⁵⁹ *any* argument or position under consideration is inherently prone to “ambiguity,” and hence so is its opposite position—even if one position seems more convincing than the other.⁶⁰ Although it seems that the Pyrrhonian position would not assert just why opposition happens (since this would, itself, imply a judgment—one that could be disputed in itself), Theodore claims that the Sceptics—who, as he argues, inherit their position from Plato⁶¹—“see that everything is in a state of flux and that nothing at all stands immovably still so as to preserve any essence and knowledge unchanged.”⁶² One can recognize the parallel here to Gregory's overarching stance that philosophers focused on the natural world are endlessly prone to opposite positions: here Theodore ascribes this position to the Sceptic who, recognizing this reality, applies this to all argumentation.

Even when Theodore affirms the Sceptics' position following on the state of flux in all things, he denotes the one, sole exception which guarantees truth: “wisdom concerning God and divine matters, which is entirely from some divine inspiration from above.”⁶³ Implicitly what is communicated from God and “divine matters” stands outside what is necessarily in flux and prone to instability. Theodore's exception notably precludes logical demonstrations—thus implicitly theological definitions that are the conclusions of deductive reasoning—alongside inferences drawn from the realm of nature and experience.⁶⁴ On the one hand this is similar to the Sceptics' resignation of accepting “the affective sense-impressions (κατὰ φαντασίαν παθητικὴν) which induce our assent involuntarily”—in other words living by the appearances that do not imply judgment,

⁵⁸ Theodore Metochites, *Sem.* 61, 6,1–8; trans. Wahlgren, modified. Cf. translation and analysis in Bydén (2002) 185 ff.

⁵⁹ Although he adopts the same position, e.g. in *Sem.* 61, 12,10–12: “It is obvious that it is this [i.e. the possibility for opposing arguments and positions] that has created the different schools of philosophy, with their traceless and implacable strifes; and it is this that has led to struggles of life and to philosophical spectacles (θέατρα φιλοσοφίας)” (trans. Wahlgren).

⁶⁰ Cf. Metochites' paraphrase of the Sceptics' position, *Sem.* 61, 6,18–21, as “namely that nothing is certain among men of those things which in every case are believed and talked about by everyone as if they could be apprehended (ληπτῶν) very clearly; further, that nothing is unshakeable and unsusceptible to opposite arguments and irrefutable in accordance with a totally sound and unchangeable truth (μετ' ἀληθείας ἀνόσου παντάπασι καὶ ἀτρέπτου)” (trans. Wahlgren, modified).

⁶¹ Theodore Metochites, *Sem.* 61, 6,9–8,20. Cf. Trizio (2019) 604–605; Bydén (2002) 190–196.

⁶² Theodore Metochites, *Sem.* 61, 10,8–9; trans. Wahlgren, modified. Cf. Bydén (2002) 187–191. As Bydén notes in n. 24, Sextus rather repudiates Plato in *PH* 1.221–225 and Heraclitus in *PH* 1.210–212.

⁶³ Theodore Metochites, *Sem.* 61, 10,12–13; see also 10,22–24.

⁶⁴ Theodore Metochites, *Sem.* 61, 10,13–17, esp.: “For even on this account, everything proffered by those earlier men, who trust their vain insight and the guidance of some kind of wisdom based on logical demonstration (ἀποδείξεων), does not seem to be unshakeable [...]” (trans. Wahlgren). See also Metochites' *Stoicheiosis Astronomikḗ* 1.2, fol. 12^r, where he defines the objects of theology (τὰ πρῶτα θεῖα) as “simple, non-deducible, and only intelligible (νοητὰ), above scientific knowledge (ἐπιστήμην) and discursive thought (διάνοιαν)”: cf. Bydén (2002) 189–190, esp. nn. 20–21.

as discursivity would suggest.⁶⁵ However if we go back to Theodore's positive statements about mathematics, this would also seem to be an exception similar to Theodore's demarcation of "God and divine matters"—even though he does not raise it here. Initially this may seem to be an implicit conflict, or perhaps not relevant here considering the rhetorical force of the sceptical position in *Semeiosis* 61.⁶⁶ However another possibility is that Theodore considers the objects of mathematics, in themselves, "divine," or certainly related, inasmuch as they are eternal and stable, as unrelated to matter—as underlined toward the end of *Semeiosis* 22.⁶⁷ Although the scope of Theodore's affirmation of scepticism in *Semeiosis* 61 appears to be universal, even in cases like logical demonstrations concerning "divine matters" which do not depend on changeable matter, Theodore's sceptical arguments rather appear to be focused on cases conditioned by change and instability: namely, both the objects of thought prone to change (esp. natural sciences) and the subjects inquiring into their objects of thought. Hence, even if one studies mathematics—which involves objects that are eternal and stable in their own nature—the degree to which one needs sensible matter to understand mathematics, and hence the aptitude with which one is able to progress, will necessarily vary and thus imply vulnerability to instability and change.

Looking back at the two sceptical positions we set out earlier, represented by Clement and Gregory Nazianzen, Theodore's position approximates more closely with Gregory's inasmuch as the former affirms a pessimistic reading of philosophy—and to the degree that Theodore explicitly affirms divine illumination as the only criterion of certainty, outside any connection to philosophy. On the other hand, Theodore's endorsement of mathematics would seem to contrast with this picture: mathematicians, once they have mastered the science, have access to certainty and truth, in much the same way as one who abides by divine revelation would seem to. So far in our texts we have not seen how Theodore connects the study of objects of mathematics to the objects of theology—if indeed they are so explicitly connected for Theodore. Insofar, though, as he seems to relate the two, and to the degree that he suggests that the human intellect can contemplate mathematical objects outside the need for divine illumination, Theodore's position approximates closer to a more positive view of philosophy, as in Clement. Perhaps further in this direction (and beyond Clement), Theodore's sceptical views come about rather *not* from the lack of direct access to divine revelation (though that is an important backdrop), but rather from the very nature of the enmattered world as the source of instability and uncertainty.⁶⁸ In this sense we find a kind of *positive* argument for a sceptical view of reason, apart from divine revelation, rather than a *negative* one, as offered in Gregory—and, as we just saw earlier, in Nicholas of Methone.

⁶⁵ Sextus Empiricus, *PH* I.10, esp. 19. See also Bydén (2002) 189–190 and 198 n. 54, who argues that Metochites comes close to a "conformist fideism" in this regard—however with the caveat that, unlike the Pyrrhonians, or post-Reformation thinkers like Erasmus and Montaigne, Metochites would still adhere to determinate dogmatic positions in Orthodox Christian beliefs, roughly following on what can be held with certainty from divine revelation.

⁶⁶ As Bydén (2002) 188–189 concludes.

⁶⁷ See esp. Theodore Metochites, *Sem.* 22, 198,18–30.

⁶⁸ Concurring with Bydén's judgment that Theodore's form of scepticism is not Pyrrhonian, strictly speaking: see below pp. 25–26.

Gregory Palamas: Philosophy and Scepticism Between the Orders of Grace and Nature

Although Theodore Metochites is roughly contemporary with Gregory Palamas, Theodore's approach in certain ways comes as a stark contrast to Palamas'—despite the fact that both agree in principle about the domain of certainty pertaining to God and divine things alone.⁶⁹ As we will see, Palamas was implicitly against the kind of sceptical position that denied direct knowledge of God—one factor motivating Palamas' well-known metaphysical distinction between the essence (οὐσία) and activities (ἐνέργεια) in God: for Palamas, the transcendence of God beyond natural knowledge or comprehension does not imply the denial of *every* kind of knowledge. Instead, the direct apprehension of God is possible in virtue of God's manifestation through the divine activities (ἐνέργεια).⁷⁰ Palamas thus stood strongly against the notion that philosophy or human reason could apprehend God—and in this sense strongly maintained a sceptical stance, following those like Gregory Nazianzen—yet he also maintained a positive, epistemologically certain means of knowledge in relation to God—in certain ways a juxtaposition to the sceptical position.

One important backdrop to Palamas' position lies in Barlaam of Calabria (c. 1290–1348 CE), Palamas' first, main opponent during the Hesychast Controversy.⁷¹ Palamas first encountered Barlaam in the latter's anti-Latin defense of the Greek Orthodox position that the Holy Spirit (as the third divine person of the Trinity) proceeds from the Father alone (as opposed to the *Filioque* position, i.e. from the Father and the Son/*Logos*). Barlaam's defense of the Greek position involved the claim that apodeictic arguments cannot be applied to God or divine matters, since God, properly speaking, transcends all things, while the premises of demonstrations can only be formulated from principles grasped by the intellect. Hence, only dialectical arguments involving shared principles (e.g. from Holy Scriptures) could be valid in the case of God.⁷²

Barlaam's view on demonstrations and their relation to God in some ways mirrors certain trends we saw in Metochites: namely the idea that the intellect could directly apprehend God only through divine illumination or revelation, or through philosophical means in ways that do not

⁶⁹ Although testimonia from Palamas' encomiast, Philotheos Kokkinos, claim the connection, Theodore appears not to have been a teacher of Palamas, but rather of Palamas' eventual critic, Nikephoros Gregoras (c. 1295–1360 CE)—who, it appears, adopted much of Theodore's sceptical viewpoint about human knowledge and the certainty possessed in divine revelation (cf. Russell (2019), pp. 113–115, and Demetracopoulos (2017)). As we will see, Palamas almost certainly seems to be responding to aspects of Metochites' framework in his critiques of Barlaam, alongside Gregoras. Additionally, Gregoras' dogmatic scepticism appears to have motivated Nicholas Kabasilas (c. 1323–after 1391 CE) to write the anti-sceptical treatise, *On the Criterion of Truth, Whether It Exists or Not, Against the Accursed Pyrrho* (c. 1354/61). It would also seem that Gregoras' sceptical framework lay behind his opposition (following Barlaam) to Palamas' positive claim for the possibility of perceiving God in bodily senses (much less intellectually). On this see Bydén (2002) 204–207 and Demetracopoulos (2017); cf. Golitsis (2019) 39.

⁷⁰ For the philosophical framework behind Palamas' distinction, see Bradshaw (2004), esp. 229–242, and Russell (2019) 112 ff.

⁷¹ On Barlaam, see Trizio (2017).

⁷² And thus the conclusion that the Latins could not defend the *Filioque* position, due both to no shared premises for dialectical argumentation, and no valid possibility for demonstrative arguments: on this see Sinkewicz (1982), esp. 188–196; Trizio (2017); Russell (2019) 114–115; Kappes (Forthcoming).

depend on the natural world (e.g. mathematics, as for Metochites)—while contrariwise, positive knowledge pertaining to God, derived through the senses or even intellection, is impossible due to God’s transcendence.⁷³ Barlaam builds on this background by claiming that “one is the truth through all things”: in other words, the same object is aimed at either unmediated through divine revelation or mediately through the practice of philosophy (the latter of which Barlaam maintains as fitting for all humans after the apostles).⁷⁴ In this, Barlaam’s claim is reminiscent of Clement’s earlier position on the unity of truth in both the pagan philosophical schools and “true philosophy” revealed by the *Logos*, where reason has the ability to access both domains by its own means.⁷⁵ In Barlaam’s vision, both the pagan and Christian do have access to God, albeit in the soul’s ascent through logic till it reaches its end in complete “unknowing” (ἀγνωσία), and in this sense, for Barlaam, becomes “assimilated to God.”⁷⁶ Barlaam’s framework thus involves a paradox: on the one hand he denies that there can be any direct apprehension of God, both through intellect and logic, yet he maintains that logic and intellect are necessary for the soul to reach the state where it can come closest to knowing God—i.e. through “unknowing.”⁷⁷

Barlaam’s framework explains his opposition to the Hesychasts (whom Palamas represents and defends), who maintained that the direct perception and knowledge of God in this life is possible, and should be pursued, while also holding to the transcendence of God.⁷⁸ This meant that instances like the divine light perceived in the Transfiguration of Christ were a direct manifestation of God (and thus “uncreated”),⁷⁹ implying that participation in God directly involved the senses in relation to the divine light, as well as the intellect’s apprehension of God in the light. On this basis, the Hesychasts claimed that the continual use of the senses, in their specific movements of prayer, were necessary for the soul’s perfection and union with God—rather than merely as an intermediate stage in the soul’s ascent. By contrast for Barlaam, this emphasis on the senses rather blinds the soul and impairs its perfection, since the soul cannot perceive intelligible objects clearly without its complete separation from the body: the

⁷³ A theme one may also see in Barlaam’s (and Palamas’) contemporary, Gregoras, even though Gregoras was an opponent of Barlaam early in the Hesychast Controversy: see Demetracopoulos (2017) and cf. earlier n. 69.

⁷⁴ Barlaam *apud* Gregory Palamas, *Pro hesychastis* II.1.5, 1–6: “But, [Barlaam] says, the sayings of the divine performers (θεουργῶν) and the wisdom that resides in them look toward one object (σκοπὸν) with the philosophy of the pagan disciplines and have reached the same end: the discovery of the truth. For one is the truth through all things, given in principle to the apostles in an unmediated way, and discovered by us through diligence (ἐπιμελείας).” Cf. Trizio (2011) 132–133. One also finds a loose parallel in Metochites’ claim, in *Sem.* 22, that the objects of mathematics are successfully aimed at despite the variations of people, custom, or sensible matter: cf. above, pp. 14–15.

⁷⁵ Cf. above, pp. 3–5, 8, and esp. n. 14.

⁷⁶ See Trizio (2011), esp. 124–125, and Ierodiakonou (2002) 228.

⁷⁷ Barlaam’s emphasis on reaching God by “unknowing” reflects his late Neoplatonic heritage: see Trizio (2011) and (2019) 606–610 for a thorough discussion of Barlaam’s use of late Neoplatonists (esp. Proclus and Syrianus) in his appropriation of Plato and Socratic “double-ignorance.”

⁷⁸ On the history of the Hesychast movement, see Krausmüller (2006).

⁷⁹ See Russell (2019) 153–159 on the history of the dispute around the uncreated status of the divine light at Mount Tabor.

“unknowing” necessary for the soul necessitates transcending the senses and all discursivity.⁸⁰ Thus the Hesychasts for Barlaam would represent rather a *reversion* away from perfection rather than assent toward perfection.⁸¹

All this helps to fill in the context which Palamas works in and is responding to in his claims about the nature of philosophy and human reason, where we find his implicit sceptical rejoinder to Barlaam’s framework. This comes out particularly in his *Pro Hesychastis*, where Palamas, in setting out his defense of the Hesychasts against Barlaam, begins by delineating what relation philosophy has to God and humans. Palamas begins by summarizing Barlaam’s position: namely that monks should pursue pagan wisdom (ἔξω σοφίαν), since perfection and holiness only happen through seeking “knowledge from all quarters (πανταχόθεν),” for knowledge is a “gift from God” (δῶρον Θεοῦ).⁸² Palamas goes on to show how, despite conceding that philosophy is a “gift” in a certain sense, it can only be so-called derivatively rather than chiefly (κυρίως): for philosophy pertains to the natural order (φυσικόν), rather than the order of grace, or the spiritual (πνευματικόν).⁸³ As he defines it, what belongs to the natural order involves exercise (μελέτη) and effort in a way that does not belong to the spiritual order: hence the former implies that only certain people, not necessarily all, will be fully capable of acquiring a character or virtue well (καλῶς) (or badly), even while the faculty or capacity is given to all alike.⁸⁴ By contrast, what is “chiefly” a gift from God and properly belongs to the spiritual order (πνευματικόν) does not involve exercise (μελέτη), but brings about its effect immediately: thus Palamas’ examples that “even simple fishermen” become “sons

⁸⁰ See e.g. Barlaam, *Epistulae* IV 372,16–18. Cf. Trizio (2011) 113 ff., where he references Proclus’ *Alcibiades Commentary* 224, 1–4, as one source behind the latter Barlaam references: “The descent of the soul into the body has removed the soul itself from the order of divine causes, from which it was filled with intellection, power, and purity, and it joins together with the fashioner (γενεσιουργῷ) by nature and material realities, from which it is filled with forgetfulness, error, and ignorance.” Barlaam’s (and Proclus’) language here is strongly reminiscent of Nicholas’ claim (above) that the soul’s lack of separation from the body results in its lack of access to perfect, complete knowledge. It is striking how both Nicholas and Barlaam implicitly follow Proclus on this point—although Nicholas attributes this state to the Fall of man, suggesting a moral imperfection blinding man, rather than a complete ontological imperfection (which Barlaam seems to imply).

⁸¹ Barlaam *apud* Gregory Palamas, *Pro hesych.* II.1.37, 8–12. Cf. Trizio (2011) 125 ff.

⁸² Gregory Palamas, *Pro hesych.* I.1, prologue. While the phrase almost certainly goes back to Barlaam in this immediate context, the line goes back both to Clement of Alexandria (cf. above, p. 3 and n. 8) and ultimately to Plato’s *Timaeus* 47b1–2: “These pursuits have given us philosophy, a gift from the gods to the mortal race whose value neither has been nor ever will be surpassed” (trans. Zeyl). Cf. Golitsis (2019) 21, n. 9, who notes that Palamas “also contradicts indirectly George Pachymeres (1242–after 1309), who tacitly quotes the *Timaeus* in the proem of his *Philosophia*.”

⁸³ Gregory Palamas, *Pro hesych.* I.1.21, 16–26: “Similarly if you put to good use that part of pagan wisdom which has been well excised, no evil will result, for it will naturally have become a tool for a given good. But in this sense it cannot be principally called a gift of God (Θεοῦ κυρίως δῶρον) and something pertaining to the spiritual (πνευματικόν), inasmuch as it belongs to what pertains to nature (φυσικόν) and is not sent from on high” (trans. Gendle, modified).

⁸⁴ Gregory Palamas, *Pro hesych.* I.1.22, 4–10: “The knowledge (γνώσις) that comes from pagan learning (ἔξω παιδείας), even if well-used, is a gift of nature, and not of grace—a gift given by God to all commonly through nature, and further developed by exercise (μελέτη). This last point—that, among all people, it does not come to maturity (παραγίνεσθαι) without effort and exercise—is an evident proof that it is therefore a gift that pertains to nature (φυσικόν), but not to the spiritual (πνευματικόν)” (trans. Gendle, modified).

of Thunder,”⁸⁵ and the apostle Paul’s turn from persecution to the reception of the ineffable vision of God.⁸⁶ These cases, as Palamas tries showing, demonstrate that salvation and knowledge of God were attained without extra exercise on the recipients’ part—and consequently without the apparent need or use for knowledge from philosophy, which otherwise requires “exercise.”

One of the main thrusts of Palamas’ distinction here is the nature of the result being either contingent or always the same, where the need for “exercise” for a natural gift so implies contingency in its result, in contrast to the “spiritual” gifts which imply the same result by their presence. Palamas recognizes that perfection for a natural gift, like knowledge from reason or intellect, is possible, but is finally contingent by its own nature on the agent developing a natural gift well or badly: i.e. the exercise of “natural gifts” can result in “good” or “bad,” like true or false knowledge. This comes out with Palamas’ example of the demons who have their intellects created by God—thus “good” by nature—however their activity (ἐνέργεια) is not from God, since they so “exercised” and used their intellect for evil.⁸⁷ In much the same way, the pagan philosophers, despite their attempts to aim at truth, end up attaining only partial truth, at best, and in the end still misappropriate the demons for gods instead of recognizing the one true God.⁸⁸ In this, Palamas takes up one of Barlaam’s premises that the ascent in philosophy implies “exercise,” or “diligence” (ἐπιμέλεια):⁸⁹ although this is the case, Palamas agrees, exercise can still be done well or badly without recourse to the “spiritual” gifts transcending nature. Bringing this to the relation of faith and reason, the presence of spiritual gifts, like faith, then becomes the criterion by which certain truths, which could otherwise be reached through natural gifts (like reason, in engaging in philosophy), can be ascertained with certainty. Natural gifts, by contrast, are susceptible to mixed truths and falsehoods—or good and evil—and cannot so imply such certainty.

One sees this in Palamas’ emphasis of opposites resulting from those who exercise their capacity for human knowledge: for instance in the philosophers who affirm “the same things to be at once animate and inanimate, endowed with and deprived of reason, [...] and [say that] things which in no manner have sensation by nature [...] are able to contain our souls.”⁹⁰ This is also mirrored in Palamas’ *One Hundred and Fifty Chapters*, where he claims that the rational soul, although possessing life essentially, is “susceptible of opposites—namely good and evil”: hence the soul does not possess goodness by its essence (οὐσία), but is rather contingent on the state of goodness

⁸⁵ Palamas, borrowing from Gregory Nazianzen (*Oration* 41.14, PG:36, 448C), references the Gospel of Mark 3:17, where Jesus first appointed the twelve apostles, including the fishermen, James and John, “the sons of thunder.”

⁸⁶ Gregory Palamas, *Pro hesych.* I.1.22, 10–18. Palamas’ example of “fishermen” (ἀλιεῦσιν) who receive the gift of God (lines 11–12)—as juxtaposed with the philosopher who attains truth—recalls Nicholas of Methone’s own juxtaposition of “unlearned men and fishermen (ἀλιεῖς)” who are the teachers of the true, revealed faith, rather than philosophers (*Refutation* 1,12–13).

⁸⁷ Gregory Palamas, *Pro hesych.* I.1.19, 12–20. One can detect an echo here of Palamas’ metaphysical distinction between essence (οὐσία) and activity (ἐνέργεια), in this case applied to creatures.

⁸⁸ Gregory Palamas, *Pro hesych.* I.1.18, 1–7.

⁸⁹ Cf. earlier n. 74, with Barlaam’s own use of “diligence” (ἐπιμέλεια).

⁹⁰ Gregory Palamas, *Pro hesych.* I.1.18, 21–31; trans. Gendle, modified. It should be noted here that Palamas’ critique is not that there are opposing positions claimed between philosophers (as in Metochites or the Sceptics), but rather that philosophers attribute opposite predicates of objects: for Palamas, in understanding the full truth of things, this suggests an imperfection from the philosophers’ side.

or evil which it possesses as a quality.⁹¹ By contrast, God as the supreme intellect, for Palamas, transcends all opposites and hence possesses goodness by his essence (οὐσία):⁹² God possesses goodness necessarily, while creatures possess goodness only contingently—i.e. through their exercise and possession of goodness as an acquired quality. This would illuminate Palamas’ discussion of the “spiritual gifts,” above: as unmediated and coming directly from God, and insofar as they directly communicate their effect without the capacity for opposites, they ultimately reflect God’s character for Palamas—or in Palamas’ metaphysical scheme, they are identified with God, to the degree that God is manifested through his activities (ἐνέργεια), while properly speaking remaining transcendent by essence (οὐσία).⁹³

The relevance of this background factors into Palamas’ statements about what can be held with certainty through demonstration—and from the inverse side, how no certain knowledge can be derived purely from the natural realm. Recalling Barlaam’s claim about demonstrations with regard to God, one of Palamas’ main rejoinders against Barlaam’s theory was to assert that demonstrative premises about God could, indeed, be formulated: in fact, Palamas makes the stronger claim that demonstrations cannot be formulated from anything in the created world, since all its objects are perishable:

Again, premises must contain a necessary term (τὸ ἀναγκάσιον), since a demonstration in the main sense, according to Aristotle, is based on things that are both necessary and eternal—that is to say everlasting beings (τῶν ἀεὶ ὄντων). [...] For such are in a real sense necessary terms, while what is always is without beginning and interminable. For in the case of something which was, when it was not, and something which will be, when it will not be, how is it always? And how is it a necessary thing? Such an item does not belong to beings and created things. Therefore no demonstration is based on any [of these cases], since even Aristotle says from his treatise, “demonstration does not belong to perishable things,” and the conclusion of a demonstration must be imperishable and eternal.⁹⁴

Although Palamas implicitly gives Aristotle a new interpretation with his claim that premises depend on eternal entities—not just eternal universals which inhere in perishable things, as Aristotle would maintain⁹⁵—one of the outcomes of Palamas’ claim is that demonstrations,

⁹¹ Gregory Palamas, *Capita 150* 33, 1–5. On Palamas’ *Capita* against the backdrop of philosophy’s renewal in 14th-century Byzantium, see Sinkewicz (1986).

⁹² Gregory Palamas, *Capita 150* 34, 1–4.

⁹³ See earlier, n. 70.

⁹⁴ Gregory Palamas, *Second Letter to Barlaam* 56, 292,16–25 (Christou et al.). Cf. Ierodiakonou (2002), esp. discussion in 229–235 (with n. 39).

⁹⁵ See e.g. Aristotle, *Posterior Analytics* I.8, 75b24–26.

properly speaking, can only be based on God as the necessary, eternally existent entity.⁹⁶ In Palamas' account syllogisms could then be made about God, because—unlike Barlaam—the direct apprehension of God, necessary for the first demonstrative premise, is indeed possible, both from revelation and through the saints' direct participation in God (and effectively one of the main claims of the Hesychasts, as we saw above).

One result of this is that all, subsequent knowledge of things in the world finally depend on God as the “necessary term” for all demonstrative knowledge. If we go back to Barlaam's claim that “all truth is one,” in Palamas' framework this would have to be qualified: though all disciplines, including pagan, “outside” wisdom, *aim at* the same truth, they inherently lack the first premise necessary for demonstration—either held by faith, through revelation, or as directly apprehended and known by the saints. This would imply that all subsequent knowledge, both sensible as well as mathematical and intelligible, is contingent and incomplete in their own domains.⁹⁷ This makes sense of Palamas' metaphor of philosophy being like the “flesh of serpents” which contain “no better and more useful medicine” among other means of healing: the serpent must first be killed, with its head and tail cut off, so that its flesh can be of use as a medicinal solution to the doctor.⁹⁸ Palamas' metaphor is telling: on the one hand, he agrees philosophy is the best medicine for a patient—but its application depends on a higher source in the form of the doctor who knows how to “manage” philosophy, i.e. who already possesses the criterion of truth and wisdom.

Looking back over Palamas in relation to our paradigm cases of Clement of Alexandria and Gregory of Nazianzen in the beginning, Palamas in one sense seems more aligned with the negative scepticism we saw in Gregory. One even finds, for example, a direct reference to Gregory's phrase, “to every argument there is a counter-argument,” in the beginning of Palamas' *Pro Hesychastis*, used in a similar vein to attack the notion of certain truth in arguments alone.⁹⁹ To this degree, Palamas seems to adhere to Theodore Metochites' scepticism of the knowledge derived from the sensible world—albeit, for Palamas, extended to the *whole* created world (both intelligible as well as sensible). In turn, Palamas certainly picks up the antagonistic theme against “pagan wisdom” found in Nicholas of Methone's own polemic against Proclus and pagan

⁹⁶ Cf. Ierodiakonou (2002) 234, who points out various respects in which Palamas departs from, and seemingly distorts, Aristotle's logic; more generally on Palamas on demonstrations, see Sinkewicz (1982) 198–202 and Petridou and Terezis (2020). Palamas' claim that logical demonstrations ultimately depend on eternal, necessarily existent entities finds precedence in Proclus' *Parmenides Commentary* 980,2–981,20, where Proclus claims that the beginning of demonstrations depends on the “common element” deriving from one, transcendent Form which is distinct from the mortal entities in which the “element” resides. (Special thanks to Antonio Vargas for pointing this out.) As with Aristotle, Proclus' claim depends on his underlying, ontological theory of universals: namely, unlike an Aristotelian framework (i.e. universals residing solely in particulars—no dependence on prior, transcendent Forms or thoughts in the mind of God), universals in perishable particulars depend on a transcendent, eternal Form. Palamas' argument in the *Second Letter* thus follows a similar, Platonist line of thought. See also Kappes (Forthcoming), who points out a textual parallel to the *Second Letter's* argument in the *Corpus Hermeticum*, Fr. 2A.

⁹⁷ Once more, reminiscent of Clement of Alexandria's claim of pagan philosophy's contingency on “true philosophy” from the *Logos*: cf. above pp. 3–5, 8–9, and n. 14. Special thanks to an anonymous reader for pointing out this parallel.

⁹⁸ Gregory Palamas, *Pro hesych.* I.1.20.

⁹⁹ Gregory Palamas, *Pro hesych.* I.1.1, 12–17. Cf. Calvário (2017) 785–786.

philosophy overall. And furthermore, inasmuch as Palamas has indeed been portrayed as an anti-rationalist, Palamas' appeal to Nazianzen's negative scepticism would seem apt.¹⁰⁰

However, from what we have seen, Palamas demonstrates a more balanced position despite his anti-philosophical rhetoric.¹⁰¹ In particular, Palamas' more positive notion of knowledge for God is noteworthy, inasmuch as revelation by faith is not the only criterion of truth, but also rather the possibility of *direct* knowledge or apprehension of God by means of the "spiritual gifts." In a certain sense this makes Palamas the least sceptical author (at least concerning the divine realm) when compared to the previous Byzantine figures we have analyzed. In turn, Palamas' construal of philosophy as pertaining to the "natural" order, thus as a "tool" (ὄργανον) and as medicinal in its purpose, is telling: though the tool by itself cannot determine its own limits (and hence lies in the sceptical domain, in its own right), its use is dictated only by the ruling principle—in this case, what belongs to the "spiritual" order. This then places Palamas much more in line with Clement's own characterization of the pagan philosophical schools in relation to "true philosophy" from the *Logos*, where the practice of philosophy according to any of the previous "schools" only captures a part of the whole truth. In this respect, whereas Metochites appears to set aside philosophy, in relation to the sensible world, and whereas Nicholas denigrates the possibility of complete knowledge for humans, with or without philosophy, due to the Fall, Palamas seems to hold surprisingly a more positive sense of philosophy—albeit as guided by knowledge pertaining to the "spiritual."

Conclusion: The Instrumentality of Byzantine Scepticism

This paper has so far attempted to lay out the positions of the three late Byzantines, Nicholas of Methone, Theodore Metochites, and Gregory Palamas, and show how they fit between two poles of the kind of scepticism we find in 2nd- to 4th-century early Christians: between (1) a "mild" variant (corresponding with Clement of Alexandria), which permitted that reason has a *partial* grasp of truths revealed in Christian revelation, if incomplete; and (2) a "strict" variant

¹⁰⁰ See e.g. the conclusions of Ierodiakonou (2002) and Krausmüller (2019).

¹⁰¹ In this regard, Krausmüller (2019) 64–67, who critiques Palamas' excision of discursive reason from the divine image—with intellection (νόσις) instead defining the divine image—requires qualification. In general, Krausmüller's argument seems to ignore Palamas' position on syllogisms, where God becomes the first, necessary term in demonstrative knowledge. Insofar as discursive reason involves syllogizing, it would then make sense for Palamas to claim that discursive reason *cannot* be the divine image, but instead what anchors such syllogistic reasoning: i.e. intellection of the first, unmiddled premise, pertaining to God. Furthermore, Palamas implicitly seems to accept Theodore Metochites' claim that discursive reasoning is prone to error (cf. Bydén (2002) 190, n. 21, and 223–224), and his further claim that the objects of theology are "above discursive thought" (cf. above, n. 64)—mirroring Palamas' prioritization of intellection. Palamas' claim also mirrors Proclus' position of the "One of the soul," i.e. the element directly correlating to the gods in their pure unity by which the soul unites with the divine, rather than through discursive reason (cf. Proclus, *On the Chaldean Philosophy*, Fr. 4, 211.4–13; *Timaeus Commentary* I, 246.19–247.8). Krausmüller, by contrast, cites Ps.-Dionysius (*De divinis nominibus* VII.2, 195,3–20) who maintains that human souls appropriate divine wisdom through discursive reasoning—a contrast to the Proclean claim. Hence, there seem to be differing Neoplatonic models of divine participation applied in Palamas and Ps.-Dionysius—one possible reason for the dissonance that Krausmüller otherwise locates solely in Palamas. In this regard (*pace* Krausmüller's conclusion in (2019) 67), Palamas simply seems to continue in the same lineage of Nicholas of Methone and Gregory Nazianzen in recognizing discursive reason as prone to error and dependent on a higher criterion of certainty.

(corresponding with Gregory Nazianzen), which maintained that reason has *no* grasp of truths revealed in Christian revelation. It should become clear by now that our three late-period Byzantines do not, strictly speaking, fall entirely into one camp or another, however all our figures, both early Christians and the late Byzantines we have analyzed, adhere to revelation as the determinative criterion of truth: reason, as exercised in philosophy, is prone to error and uncertainty without revelation as the criterion of certainty.

Given this, we can at least summarize how each of our three figures fit into the two poles we sketched in the beginning. Nicholas of Methone, as we saw, maintains human reason's susceptibility to error, both in its own reasoning and apart from divine illumination: this would suggest that Nicholas leans toward (2), especially insofar as he critiques Proclus and all other pagan philosophers who mistake demons for gods (esp. in polytheism), and fail to adhere to the one true God; on the other hand, Nicholas leans toward (1) insofar as he maintains that Proclus, though outside revelation as a pagan, imperfectly grasps truths that are perfectly realized in the Pseudo-Dionysius (who, Nicholas claims, is Proclus' true source), and insofar as other philosophers, such as Aristotle, are more correct in accord with truths possessed with certainty in Christian revelation.¹⁰²

Theodore Metochites, by contrast, seems to lie more with pole (2), insofar as he takes the sensible world as the source of reason being prone to error, whereas only divine inspiration and revelation is certain. On the other hand, Metochites seems to lie more with pole (1) insofar as he holds that mathematics and its objects can be known with certainty, without reliance on sensible matter, suggesting that reason *can* grasp truths with certainty, apart from revelation as the criterion.

Gregory Palamas, as we saw above, in some ways reacts against implications drawn from this latter stance by Theodore, especially as they are developed in Barlaam. Palamas thus certainly tends toward the stricter pole (2), inasmuch as he classifies reason in the natural domain (*φύσιον*), which implies the capability for opposite outcomes, and hence truth or falsehoods, rather than the certainty of truth found in the spiritual domain (*πνευματικόν*), i.e. divine illumination and revelation. In this Palamas denies the claim from those like Barlaam that "all truth is one" in the sense that philosophy, even if practiced well, can be taken as the criterion of truth in the *same* way as revelation—one might say an extreme form of Clement's own claim of the unity of truth. Yet insofar as Palamas considers human reason in philosophy to be an "instrument," and has the capability to aim at the truth, Palamas leans toward pole (1)—albeit with the prerequisite necessity for divine knowledge, either held by faith or as directly known.

In sum, we can extend Börje Bydén's conclusions about Theodore to the other Byzantine authors we have considered here: all of them adhere to a kind of negative dogmatic scepticism, according to which there remains a domain of knowledge which can be possessed with certainty. By contrast, the other domain(s) of knowledge either cannot be possessed certainly as true or false—or they cannot be so validated without the criterion of truth provided by divine inspiration or

¹⁰² At least in the case of Aristotle, one can see Nicholas' approval with his seven explicit citations of Aristotle, and implicit references to Aristotle's framework—for instance in maintaining the soul's immanent relation to body in his commentary on Prop. 82 (cf. pp. 12–13).

revelation.¹⁰³ In this regard, Bydén is right to link this trend to a broader, Christian Platonist-like theme in the background, where the created world is often described in Heraclitean-like terms as existing in a state of constant flux and instability, in contrast to the stability and certainty of God and the divine.¹⁰⁴ The provenance of this theme one can see in Plato's *Phaedo* 90B–E, where Socrates recognizes the character of things as always in flux—yet he also maintains that “we should not allow into our minds the conviction that argumentation has nothing sound about it; much rather that we should believe that it is we who are not yet sound.”¹⁰⁵ It is no surprise that this comes a few pages before Socrates critiques the natural scientists (i.e. the Presocratics) for misattributing the term, “cause” (αἴτιον), to material entities, which are rather instruments of what is more truly the “cause”—i.e. the Forms, or implicitly intellect (νοῦς).¹⁰⁶ In other words, the full explanation or reason of things in their essence cannot be their material parts, as “instruments,” but rather the separate Form which defines the correct order of the material parts in their capacity as “instruments.”

What our Byzantines seem to do is to apply this framework to the relation between faith and natural reason in its exercise of philosophy: reason in this capacity ends up as a “tool” (recalling Palamas’ terminology), while the true “cause” becomes divine revelation, beyond human reason, which employs the “tool” of philosophy in the correct way. The sceptical methods or framework employed by the varying figures we have seen then end up considering the variation of certainty—or lack thereof—that can be had in reason’s “instrumental” role.¹⁰⁷

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¹⁰³ Bydén (2002) 189–190.

¹⁰⁴ Bydén (2002) 198—agreeing with his conclusion that there is “nothing to suggest that ancient Skepticism ever attracted the interest of Byzantine intellectuals between Photios and Metochites”; see also his n. 54.

¹⁰⁵ Plato, *Phaedo* 90d9–e2; trans. Grube. Cf. Bydén (2002) 195–196.

¹⁰⁶ See esp. Plato, *Phaedo*, 99b2–6. On Plato on the notion of “cause” (αἴτιον, αἴτια) in response to his predecessors, see Menn (1992, 1995) and Sedley (1998).

¹⁰⁷ An additional point of comparison that can be made here is Thomas Aquinas’ distinction between sacred science (which exceeds reason and communicates truths by revelation) and the other, natural sciences (which reason can grasp), where the former is “most certain” by its own nature, even if only grasped by belief, or faith, and not known directly by human reason: see *Summa Theologiae* Pars I, Q1, A1; and A5, obj./resp. #1.

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